

Results on Data Apps

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Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the results obtained from the developed data apps defined in D1.1 [1] and summarises the relevant insights generated by each app. The motivation for these functional units is to uncover insights from three-phase smart meter data that can aid decision-making and enhance grid management, prioritise investments, facilitate the provision of reliable services to customers, and support the global agenda to control CO₂ emissions. These insights are also relevant to several other stakeholders, including electricians and installers who work directly on phase connections and attend to customer issues. By leveraging the three-phase smart meter datasets shared by our partners through this project, several apps have been prototyped and validated for DSOs to operationalise further.

The presented apps have been categorised into three main groups, the first group comprising data apps that are particularly for data preparation and topology refinement, thereby setting the stage for their usability in other data apps. These apps include the data extractor - for timeseries data loading and topology refinement, SM classifier for characterisation and classification of smart meters, SM phase mapper for refining per phase topology information and mapping SMs based on their voltage measurements, and data corrector serving as a data updating patch, particularly for cleaning SM profiles, phase correction and topology cleaner. The second category contains data apps for phase imbalance analytics. Hence, the phase imbalance profiler and phase imbalance analyser have been presented. The last category covers apps that help identify heavy electrification loads and the phases they are connected to. In this case, the focus was on electrical heating identification, electric vehicles, and photovoltaic panels. Running the developed data apps on large-scale datasets can require effort in some use cases; hence, the results on the scaling of the data apps with respect to datasets and compute are presented. This further exposed the opportunity to reflect on areas for further exploration.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Project background

The rapid electrification of the grid is placing more pressure on distribution networks, where increasing numbers of heat pumps, electric vehicles (EVs), and other power electronic devices introduce additional loads and often phase imbalance. At the same time, Danish distribution system operators (DSOs) generally lack detailed observability of low-voltage (LV) grids: topology records might have errors, phase-connection information is often dependent on the communication form of the meters and missing for some meters, and power quality monitoring is limited or absent at secondary substations. This lack of granular, per-phase visibility forces DSOs to rely on conservative planning assumptions, leading to unnecessary capacity buffers, delayed customer connections, and costly reinforcement measures that slow down the green transition.

Motivated by these challenges, the 3PhaseInsight project unlocks the value of per-phase smart-meter measurements by developing advanced analytics and scalable data-processing pipelines. The platform validates on a dataset of around 100,000 customers provided by Radius, a leading DSO in Denmark, demonstrating real-world performance at scale and establishing a proven foundation for broader deployment. The central idea is that modern smart meters can provide per-phase voltage, power, and harmonic information at a granularity that enables a new level of LV situational awareness. The platform delivers actionable insights through state-of-the-art data-driven and machine-learning algorithms, directly supporting more efficient operation, planning, and stakeholder-level data sharing.

The project focuses on developing and validating a suite of “data apps” including per-phase topology correction, imbalance screening, and detection of significant electrification loads, such as heat pumps and EV chargers. These analytics have been prototyped and tested in the local prototyping environment, and then integrated into an open-source, cloud-deployable data-pipeline framework that supports scalable execution, modular workflow composition, and interoperability with DSO environments. More of this framework will be described in D4.1 [2] and in the documentation of the open-source repositories¹. By combining improved LV observability with replicable digital tools, the project aims to help DSOs target interventions more precisely, design new customer-facing services, and establish a pathway for broader sector adoption and future expansion of the analytics toolbox.

1.2 Scope of the document

This deliverable covers the results and inputs of the data apps from D1.1 [1] that were actually developed. The choice of developed apps is based on their feasibility within the project’s timeframe. Other factors included the prioritisation score for each app, methodological feasibility, and relevance. While detailed results are well articulated, information on the specific algorithm used for each data app will be presented in D3.2 [3]. Additionally, results obtained from the presented data apps are based on the data specifications presented in D2.1 [4] and from the Local prototyping environment version of the data apps as described in D2.2 [5].

¹3PhaseInsight on Github: <https://github.com/3PhaseInsight>

2 Results on data apps

2.1 Results on Data Preparation and Topology Refinement

2.1.1 Data Extractor

Data Extractor is a core component of the data app pipeline, serving as the initial step for querying and reading time-series data. It handles source data that is often too large to query properly, and transforms it into per smart meter files that are compatible with the format of other data apps — making data significantly faster and less computationally heavy to load. It provides methods for retrieving time series based on filters such as *data batch* (first-, second-, or third batch), *processing stage* (raw, cleaned, or cleaned and phase-corrected), and *topology information* (e.g., cabinet, transformer, or secondary substation). In addition to querying data, Data Extractor can also store extracted datasets. Most data apps primarily use smart meter-level time series data stored using this Data App.

Input data Data Extractor retrieves data from CSV-based time series and topology datasets. The time series data includes voltage, active and reactive power (injection and consumption), and total harmonic distortion of current and voltage at a 15-minute temporal resolution per smart meter. The topology data describes the relationships among cabinets, feeders, transformers, and secondary substations and includes metadata such as smart meter-to-cabinet connections and the presence of Photovoltaic (PV) systems or heat pumps.

Output Based on selected filters, CSV time series data are extracted and converted to Parquet format using parallelized multicore processing. When topology-based filtering is applied, JSON mapping files (e.g., smart meter-to-topology mappings) are generated to facilitate efficient data selection. For queries, the extractor returns a Pandas DataFrame containing the requested time series, while persistent storage is handled in Parquet format. An exemplary results outlook is presented in Table 1 and 2.

Visualizations

Table 1: Example of mapping between smart meter ID and grid components, also called smart meter-to-topology mapping.

ID	Zip Code	Secondary Substation ID	Transformer ID	Feeder ID	...
12345	XXX	102030	405060	708090

Table 2: Example of a Pandas DataFrame smart meter profile extraction.

Timestamp	Voltage I1 [V]	Voltage I2 [V]	Voltage I3 [V]	Active Power I1 [W]	Active Power I2 [W]	...
2023-10-11 14:15	225	225	227	87	6	...
2023-10-11 14:30	225	226	227	87	7	...
2023-10-11 14:45	224	224	227	189	7	...
2023-10-11 15:00	226	226	226	23	7	...
2023-10-11 15:15	225	226	227	22	6	...
...

Insights The Data Extractor functions solely as an intermediate step between the raw data source and the data applications. It does not modify data quality, but only filters and structures the data into the requested subset formats.

Depending on other data apps, "raw", "cleaned", or "cleaned and corrected" datasets can be queried. Raw datasets refer to the original data from the Distribution System Operator (DSO); *cleaned* refers

to modified raw data with missing-value imputation and outlier replacement; and *corrected* refers to phases and relations between topology components that are revised based on voltage analysis. These dataset modifications are further described in sections 2.1.3 and 2.1.4.

Converting data from CSV to Parquet format reduces file size, improves storage efficiency, improves read performance, and simplifies integration, but does not change the underlying data content or uncertainty.

Limitations: While the the data extractor is designed to uniformize the data, if the source data is on a completely new format, the Data extractor still needs to be manually configured to be able to read the data properly.

Scaling: The data extractor implements Dask multicore processing, but still with this the possessing the source data will still take in the order of hours to compute, and it is therefore recommended to save the resulting per SM parquet files(this is the default setting), which makes the data ingestion to other Data Apps near instant

2.1.2 Smart Meter Classifier

The Smart Meter Classifier classifies, characterizes, and plots smart meters based on their time series data. The classification provides a general assessment of each smart meter, including phase connectivity and data availability. The characterization provides a more detailed analysis of each smart meter's relationship to topology units and includes an analytical evaluation of voltage, active power, and reactive power per phase.

Input data Smart Meter Classifier uses only raw time series Parquet data for each injected smart meter ID and JSON smart meter-to-topology mapping inputs. Multiple or individual smart meters can be analysed at a time. Smart meter-to-topology mapping is created using the Data Extractor.

Based on certain filters, specific smart meter IDs classified under certain criteria can be plotted.

Output Smart Meter Classifier have distinctly three distinctly different kinds of results. The first two are classification and characterization data, which are formatted as dictionaries and stored as JSON files. The third kind of results are plots of smart meter time series data, which are stored in SVG format.

- **Characterization data:** Characterization results are stored in a nested dictionary structure, where each smart meter ID is a key containing multiple sub-dictionaries with characterization information. Below is a list of the sub-dictionary keys for each smart meter ID in the Smart Meter Classifier.
 - *Topology:* topology connections for each smart meter. This includes connections to Secondary Substation ID, Transformer ID, Feeder ID and Cabinet ID.
 - *Data availability:* boolean values on availability (if smart meter IDs match IDs in time series tables) and containment of data, and numeric values on relative length (percentage of all points of data that have values) and absolute length (number of data points)
 - *Data Quality:* details on evaluated voltage, active power and reactive power per phase. Include a summary ("*good*"/"*medium*"/"*bad*" status) and percentage of missing values.
 - * They are said to have "*good*" data quality, if less than 10% of the dataset is missing
 - * "*medium*" data quality, if less than 50% is missing or
 - * "*bad*" data quality otherwise.

In addition, for every voltage per phase, the percentage that any voltage phase is below a limit of 207 Volts per time stamp, the percentage of 12 consecutive identical values (frozen fraction), and the fraction of corrupted values (either missing, frozen or below voltage threshold) are also included.

- *Data Statistics*: statistical metrics on evaluated voltages, active power and reactive power per phase. Include minimum value, maximum value, mean and standard deviation.
 - *Connectivity*: contains a list of connected phases from the injected smart meter, a list of phases which have a connection error (classified if a phase has above 95% of voltage measurements > voltage threshold), and switching phases (classified as phases which have above 192 consecutive time stamps without consumption and with consumption).
- **Classification data**: Classification results are stored in a dictionary structure, where each key represents a classification category and the value is a list of injected smart meter IDs belonging to that category. Below is a list of the classification keys used in the Smart Meter Classifier.
 - *All SMs*: all smart meter IDs in a given run.
 - *SMs with dataset containing data*: smart meters IDs that have at least one data value.
 - *SMs with dataset containing no data*: smart meters IDs that have only missing values.
 - *SMs without dataset*: smart meter IDs which are present in the list of time series data, but have no dataset.
 - *SMs with incomplete topology info*: smart meter IDs which have at least one missing connection to a topology unit.
 - *SMs with only good data quality*: smart meter IDs, if all analysed values have "good" data quality.
 - *SMs with any medium or bad data quality*: smart meter IDs, if at least one analysed value has "medium" or "bad" data quality.
 - *SMs with any bad data quality*: smart meter IDs, if at least one analysed value has "bad" data quality.
 - *SMs with 3-phase connection*: smart meter IDs which are connected to all 3 phases. A smart meter phase is considered connected if the percentage of timestamps with data points exceeds 2.5% of the recorded time series period.
 - *SMs with 2-phase connection*: smart meter IDs which are connected to only 2 phases.
 - *SMs with 1-phase connection*: smart meter IDs which are connected to only 1 phase.
 - *SMs with connection error*: smart meter IDs which have a phase classified as a connection error (see *connectivity* under characterization data).
 - *SMs with on-off switch*: smart meter IDs which have a phase classified as an off switch (see *connectivity* under characterization data).
 - **Smart meter plots**: Based on classification results, smart meters can be plotted using a set of selection filters. Each filter with a specified phase and variables yields a specific plot, which is concatenated into a single SVG image, as shown in Figure 1. Below is a list of available filters.
 - *All with dataset containing data*: plot smart meters IDs that have at least one data value.
 - *With only good data quality*: plot smart meter IDs, if all analysed values have "good" data quality.
 - *With any medium or bad data quality*: plot smart meter IDs, if at least one analysed value has "bad" data quality.

-
- *With 1-phase connection*: plot smart meter IDs which are connected to only 1 phase.
 - *With 2-phase connection*: plot smart meter IDs which are connected to only 2 phases.
 - *With connection error*: plot smart meter IDs which have a phase classified as a connection error (see *connectivity* under characterization data).
 - *With on off switch*: plot smart meter IDs which have a phase classified as an off switch (see *connectivity* under characterization data).
 - *Variable selection*: plot based on variables (voltage, active power, reactive power, or a combination).
 - *Phase selection*: plot specific phases (only one phase, all phases, or a combination).

Visualizations

Figure 1: Plotted unspecified smart meter ID with only good quality. All phases are plotted with sub-figures for the voltage, active power, and reactive power.

Limitations The output of Smart Meter Classifier is based on several hard-set thresholds.

- Limit defining what counts as having "no data" is 2.5%,
- "good" data is classified as having less than 10% missing,

-
- "medium" data is classified as having less than 50% missing,
 - *lower voltage limit* is set to 207 Volts,
 - *offset-threshold* is classified as more than 95% of the recorded voltage is below or equal to the voltage limit,
 - a constant period is defined as 192 consecutive timestamps (48 hours with a 15-minute timestamp granularity) having data or no data, and
 - a frozen range is defined as the same value occurring for 12 consecutive or more time stamps (3 hours with a 15-minute timestamp granularity).

Many of classifications and characterizations are entirely dependent on these thresholds. The thresholds are, however, flexible, so the users can adjust these parameters depending on how strict or lenient they desire them to be.

Scaling Smart Meter Classifier can process multiple smart meters in parallel using Dask, with a runtime of up to 7 smart meter IDs per second. Running all 61,557 IDs from the second batch's smart meters with 4 parallel Intel i5-10300H cores @ 4 GB RAM each, can therefore take a little over half an hour.

It is possible to characterize and classify smart meter IDs without topology information. This would leave the sub-dictionary *Topology* in the characterization data empty.

2.1.3 Smart Meter Phase Mapper

Smart Meter Phase Mapper refines existing per-phase topology information by examining all smart meter phase-voltage measurements within a transformer and grouping them by profile similarity. Phases that are electrically close are typically supplied by the same transformer phase (I1, I2, I3) and feeder, and exhibit higher correlations. By analysing the dataset, the data app can map phases from a transformer, a phase twist, a double connection, and wrongly allocated feeders/transformers/cabinet units in an existing topology, and mappings can also be updated.

This data app helps ensure the correct operational topology is in place, which in turn supports more accurate follow-up analytics. Wrong phase mappings are a common problem during the transition from electric metres to smart metres.

Input data Smart Meter Phase Mapper uses raw time-series Parquet data from each injected transformer ID to analyse voltage levels, JSON smart meter-to-topology mapping inputs for smart meter-topology relations, and Smart Meter Classifier results for smart meter IDs from the investigated transformers to extract a list of unconnected phases.

The primary user-defined inputs are a list of desired transformer IDs to be analysed and the topology processing level, which can be either "raw" or "cleaned" (see section 2.1.4).

Output Two results are returned: a topology mapping in CSV format, and a dendrogram showcasing the mapping in SVG format.

- **Topology Mapping:** Topology mapping returns a CSV-based DataFrame. Each column contributes to explaining the current topological relationships among smart meters, feeders, cabinets, and transformers, as well as updated information.
 - *Transformer ID:* transformer supplying power to the investigated smart meter.
 - *Feeder ID:* feeder supplying power to the investigated smart meter.

- *Cabinet ID*: cabinet supplying power to the investigated smart meter.
- *Smart meter ID*: investigated the smart meter, which topology unit it relates to.
- *Smart meter phase*: investigated phase from specified smart meter ID.
- *Feeder phase*: actual feeder phase connected to smart meter phase based on mapping analysis.
- *Transformer phase*: actual transformer phase connected to feeder phase based on mapping analysis.
- *True feeder ID*: actual feeder ID based on mapping analysis. Only feeder IDs connected to the transformer ID under investigation are analysed. If no compatible supplying feeder is found, then it returns NaN.
- *True transformer ID*: actual transformer ID based on mapping analysis. If this is not the same as the existing, it returns "other".
- *Likely cabinet ID*: likely cabinet ID based on mapping analysis. This refers to other cabinet IDs connected to the same transformer. If not, then it returns none.
- *Status*: this returns a classification of the results. Can be either
 - * **"Normal"**, if all existing topology information match the analysed smart meter phase.
 - * **"Wrong Feeder"** if a mismatch is detected between the voltage profile of the analysed smart meter phase and what is expected for the connected feeder. A suggested alternative feeder (within the same transformer) is provided in the *True feeder ID* column, and a possible matching cabinet in the *True cabinet ID*.
 - * **"Wrong Trafo"** for a mismatch between the voltage profile of the smart meter phase and all feeders and cabinets. This suggests that power is provided elsewhere than given in the topology information.
 - * **"Smart meter phase twist"** for a mismatch between the given phase (I1, I2 or I3) for the smart meter and the analysed voltage profile for the feeder and transformer.
 - * **"Unconnected Phases"** for phases that, according to results from Smart Meter Classifier, have a connection error (see section 2.1.2) and therefore no analysis can be done (this result in NaNs in Feeder phase, Transformer phase, True feeder ID and True transformer ID) and are often also followed with the status **"Smart Meter Phase Insufficient Data"**.
 - * **"Unknown Feeder"** if no match between the smart meter voltage profile can be matched with any feeder profile for any phase within the the same transformer. This might suggest that the smart meter are either provided by an external feeder, or an undocumented feeder exist within transformer.
 - * **"Smart Meter Phase Doubled"** for two phase voltage profiles that match within the same smart meter. This suggest that the two identical smart meter phases are provided by the same feeder phase.

It is possible for a phase to be classified in several categories.

- **Dendrogram**: A visual depiction of the phase mapping is shown as a subset of a transformer with several topology discrepancies. Each cluster in the dendrogram is coloured according to the supplying feeder. Each leaf within a cluster is named after the phase, smart meter ID, cabinet ID and feeder ID.

For any *Status* other than "Normal", "Unknown Feeder", or "Unconnected Phases", a red box encapsulates the nodes, with the status text below explaining the updated mapping.

Visualizations

Figure 2: A dendrogram depicting an unspecific investigated transformer.

Table 3: Anonymized example of a CSV DataFrame topology mapping results of a run with several transformer IDs.

Trafo ID	Feeder ID	Cabinet ID	SM ID	SM Phase	Feeder Phase	Trafo Phase	True Feeder ID	True Trafo ID	Likely Cabinet ID	Status
...
768491	654203	901274	442987	13	13	13	654203	768491	...	Normal
768491	654203	318650	775412	11	11	11	654203	768491	...	Normal
768491	654203	318650	775412	12	12	12	654203	768491	...	Normal
768491	654203	318650	775412	13	13	13	654203	768491	...	Normal
768491	654203	318650	590841	11	13	13	882104	768491	440976	SM Phase Twist / Wrong Feeder
768491	654203	318650	590841	12	12	12	882104	768491	440976	Wrong Feeder
768491	654203	318650	590841	13	11	11	882104	768491	440976	SM Phase Twist / Wrong Feeder
768491	216775	934180	687522	11	NaN	NaN	NaN	other	...	Wrong Trafo
768491	216775	934180	687522	12	NaN	NaN	NaN	other	...	Wrong Trafo
768491	216775	934180	687522	13	NaN	NaN	NaN	other	...	Wrong Trafo
502944	814267	399601	720384	11	11	11	814267	502944	...	Normal
502944	814267	399601	720384	12	12	12	814267	502944	...	Normal
502944	814267	399601	720384	13	13	13	814267	502944	...	Normal
502944	814267	399601	566118	11	11	11	814267	502944	...	Normal
502944	814267	399601	566118	12	12	12	814267	502944	...	Normal
502944	814267	399601	566118	13	13	13	814267	502944	...	Normal
502944	814267	399601	981203	11	11	11	814267	502944	...	Normal
...

Insights On Table 4, an analysis based on phases from 57,991 smart meters show that most phases are labelled correctly, whereas a considerable 4.9% are supplied by an unknown ID feeder. Around 1.9% exhibit undocumented smart meter or feeder phase twist. The remainder are either doubled smart meter phases, unknown transformer connections, and wrongful labelled feeders for smart meters.

Table 4: Distribution of phase mapping categories across a sample of 173,973 phases from 57,991 SMs connected to 688 transformers. A smart meter is counted in a category if at least one of its phases is classified in that category.

Category	# SMs	# Phases	% Phases
Normal	54,588	159,106	91.45%
Unknown Feeder Phase	3,132	8,462	4.86%
SM Phase Insufficient Data	1,598	2,119	1.22%
SM Phase Twist	1,427	2,220	1.28%
Feeder Phase Twist	527	1,100	0.63%
SM Phase Doubled	467	1,031	0.59%
Wrong Feeder	351	938	0.54%
Wrong Trafo	81	243	0.14%

The results demonstrate that a majority of phases are correctly labelled, but it is possible to identify a significant smart meter phases with incorrectly allocations. Especially the *Unknown Feeder Phase* indicate that a noticeable number of phases are provided electricity from unknown connections. Further analysis could reveal if this is due to undocumented feeder, other external connections, or something else entirely.

Limitations Classifications are based on spearman-correlations, for several reasons. Spearman works best for non-linear data, such as the analysed voltage data, but evaluates relationships based on monotonic functions. The voltage data can generally be assumed as constant mean with noise, and are therefore not monotonic. This assumption of comparability with monotonic relationships, might induce some uncertainties when comparing voltage profiles, which can affect result certainty.

The reason why Spearman is used, is the granularity of the data is fairly low (15-minute granularity), which pollute the underlying patterns. This means the general shape is compared rather than true monotonic patterns, which can not be captured with such a low granularity. Other reasons is Spearman's general robustness against outliers, which commonly occurs in the voltage data.

In addition, when a *wrong transformer* or *wrong feeder* is classified for a specific smart meter phase, there exist no suggestion to its true topology unit. This is due to phases only being analysed within their associated transformers. As a potential use-case in the future, phases with uncertain feeders and transformer relations could be compared to voltage profiles of nearby topology units, to accurately identify correct feeder and transformer supply.

Scaling Smart Meter Phase Mapper is able to multiprocessing transformer IDs in parallel using Dask, with run time of only up to 7 smart meter ID per second. Since the dataset size for transformer greatly vary, the mapping computation per transformer ID also fluctuates much, but averages around 12 seconds per iteration. Running all of second batch's 769 distinct transformer IDs² with 4 parallel cores can therefore take a little over 40 minutes.

2.1.4 Data Corrector

Data Corrector consists of four sub-modules with similar purposes. Each module specializes in correcting or updating a set dataset. Correcting is inferred as being either *cleaned* or *phase corrected*. The four modules are as follows:

- **Smart Meter Profile Cleaner:** cleans smart meter time series voltage, active power, and reactive power for each phase, by comprising missing data imputation and outlier detection and replacement.

²769 transformer ID in Table 3 refer to the cleaned topology set. The raw dataset enumerates 836 distinct IDs. See section 2.1.4 for details on the cleaning process.

- **Smart Meter Phase Corrector:** corrects the phase labels in the column names of individual smart meter datasets based on results from data app Smart Meter Phase Mapper and optional Smart Meter Profile Cleaner.
- **Topology Cleaner:** creates cleaned versions of the raw topology files provided by the DSO, by comprising and removing missing data.
- **Topology Phase Corrector:** corrects the phase, feeder and transformer labels and allocations in the LV topology and *Meter-And-Cabinet* CSV files, based on results from Smart Meter Phase Mapper and Topology Cleaner.

Input data Depending on the module, there exist different inputs.

- **Smart Meter Profile Cleaner:** uses either smart meter-to-topology mappings (raw, cleaned or cleaned and corrected) or Smart Meter Phase Mapper mapping results in JSON format, loads JSON characterizations results from Smart Meter Classifier, and queries Parquet raw smart meter time series data from Data Extractor.
- **Smart Meter Phase Corrector:** uses JSON results from Smart Meter Phase Mapper and either *raw* or *cleaned* Parquet smart meter time series data, queried from Data Extractor.
- **Topology Cleaner:** uses raw LV topology and raw Meter And Cabinet CSV data.
- **Topology Phase Corrector:** uses JSON results from Smart Meter Phase Mapper and cleaned topology data from Topology Cleaner.

Output

- **Smart Meter Profile Cleaner:** Produces modified Parquet smart meter time series data, with missing values and outliers imputed using either *regression*, *days around* (mean of day before and day after a NaN data input), *rolling mean* (default rolling window is set to 24 hours, or 94 time stamps) or *rolling median* methods.
 - **Smart Meter Plots:** The profile cleaner module can also produce plots, showing voltages, active power, and reactive power for each phase, indicating sessions without datasets, raw data, and their predictions for each smart meter. This is illustrated in Figure 3.
- **Smart Meter Phase Corrector:** Produces modified *raw* or *cleaned* Parquet smart meter datasets, with edited phase names based on "phase twist" results from Smart Meter Phase Mapper. In the case of "double connections", phase variables (voltage, active power, and reactive power) are combined: the voltage is averaged, and the active and reactive power are added. For NaN values, the combined column is also set to NaN.
- **Topology Cleaner:** Produces modified LV topology and *Meter And Cabinet* CSV files. LV topology is modified by adding numerical values for nodes and substation numbers, while NaN values in cable capacity, cable length, phase size, resistance, fuser size, cable type, and phase material are filled by grouping identical substations and finding the mean or recurring classifications. Duplicated rows are removed based on the one with the highest cable capacity. *Meter And Cabinet* are modified by removing rows with meter and or cabinets with NaN values.
- **Topology Phase Corrector:** Produces modified, cleaned *Meter-And-Cabinet* CSV files. LV topology is identical to the results produced in Topology Cleaner. Cabinet and feeder IDs are edited in *Meter And Cabinet* based on "wrong feeder" results from Smart Meter Phase Mapper.

Visualizations

Figure 3: Smart Meter Profile Cleaner cleaning of an unspecified smart meter. Red bars represent missing periods, black lines represent raw data, and blue lines represent predictions from a regression imputation method. No outliers are detected in this time series data.

Insights Since smart meters do not always record reliably and gaps in measurements are common, the Smart Meter Profile Cleaner serves a well-intended purpose. However, the DA does not account for potentially incorrect topology information, meaning that data imputed into missing periods may be based on incorrect neighbouring phases. To improve this, functions to implement phase-corrected data from Smart Meter Phase Mapper should be investigated more.

Limitations Smart Meter Profile Cleaner's imputations are based on previous values within the investigated smart meter and neighbouring phases of that smart meter. This produces fine results for missing values for short periods, but can induce unreliable numbers when dealing with longer periods with constant NaNs. Since many smart meters in our dataset suffer from NaNs from September to start November, predictions can often prove unrealistic with constant or continuous fluctuating values. This problem can evidently be seen on Figure 3 in the predictions of the large missing periods in the beginning and end of the time series.

Scaling Smart Meter Profile Cleaner is the most computationally heavy module of the four, with a computation averaging around 5 minutes per cleaned smart meter. In addition, due to the extensive data required to store intermediate results for the imputation methods, as well as the neighbouring phase's time series data, approximately 3.5 GB of memory is required per smart meter for computation. Even with multi-core parallel computation, a rundown of the second batch's 61,557 smart meter IDs using 4 cores and a total of 16 GB of memory will take approximately 20 hours to complete.

2.2 Results on Imbalance Analytics

2.2.1 Power Flow Tool

The Power Flow data app utilizes *Pandapower*[6] to propagate smart meter data to cabinets, feeders (collectively buses), and lines in a substation through power flow calculations. This provides time-series data on feeders, cabinets, and lines, which can be further used for insights into the grid, which is useful for additional analysis.

Input data The Power Flow Tool utilizes active- and reactive power information from raw or processed smart meter time-series Parquet data, together with CSV topology information.

Output The results from the power flow analysis are stored as Parquet time-series data covering buses and lines for the chosen grid within each substation. Each metric is stored in a separate file, containing per-phase values for both buses and lines. The analysed metrics are:

- Bus voltage magnitudes per phase (p.u.)
- Bus voltage angles per phase (degrees)
- Bus active power injection per phase (MW)
- Bus reactive power injection per phase (MVar)
- Line currents (from-side) per phase (kA)
- Line currents (to-side) per phase (kA)
- Line loading per phase (%)
- Total line loading: (%)
- Line active losses per phase (MW)

- Asymmetric load results per phase (active (MW) and reactive (MVar))
- Asymmetric static generator results per phase: (active (MW) and reactive (MVar))
- Bus Voltage imbalance factor (VUF) (%)
- Bus Current unbalance ratio (CUR) (%):
- Line Current unbalance ratio (CUR)(%)

Visualizations:

Table 5: Example of a Parquet DataFrame containing per unit bus voltages for phases L1, L2 and L3 for an unspecified substation. Each metric is saved in a separate parquet file for improved querying.

Timestamp	10980 L1	10980 L2	10980 L3	138772 L1	138772 L2	138772 L3	150362 L1	150362 L2	150362 L3
2023-11-20 08:15	0.999	1.000	1.000	0.998	0.997	0.998	1.000	0.999	1.000
2023-11-20 08:30	0.998	1.000	0.999	0.994	0.996	0.991	0.998	0.999	0.999
2023-11-20 08:45	0.998	0.999	0.997	0.993	0.995	0.993	0.997	0.999	0.998
2023-11-20 09:00	0.996	0.996	0.993	0.992	0.995	0.994	0.997	0.999	0.997
2023-11-20 09:15	0.996	0.998	0.994	0.992	0.995	0.995	0.996	0.999	0.998
...

Insights The output of the power flow is all based on standard power flow calculations and practises as used by *PowerPandas*, with the only exceptions being the CUR calculations, which are based on [7].

Limitations It should be noted that the line and bus outputs are derived from the smart meter’s time-series data, and not actual measured data. The output is therefore subject to greater scrutiny and should not be taken as real measured data. As seen in [8] there there can be significant differences between power flow results derived and actual measured values at the substation level.

Scaling The Power Flow Tool can currently parallelized by splitting the time series data temporarily and running multiple power flows in parallel, then stitching them together afterward. Additionally, as the calculations are per substation, the power flow can also be parallelized by running substations in parallel, if multiple substations are to be run.

2.2.2 Phase Imbalance Profiler

The Phase Imbalance Profiler examines the phase imbalance for buses and lines by injecting information from the Power Flow Tool and smart meter time-series data to calculate unbalance metrics and generate visualizations per substation.

Input data The Phase Imbalance Profiler utilizes generated Parquet time-series from Power Flow Tool, by either querying saved data, or calling directly if it is the first time the substations is examined.

Output The Phase Imbalance Profiler computes two phase-imbalance metrics for all lines and buses in a specified substation; the Current Unbalance Ratio (CUR) and the Voltage Unbalance Factor (VUF) [7]. Results are stored in single-value metrics in JSON format, with keys referring to buses and lines, and subkeys to each metric. PNG visualisations of the imbalance results can optionally be saved.. Metrics store per bus or line are:

- **Bus metrics:**
 - *Bus ID*: Unique identifier of each bus. This is the superkey for a specific bus within the investigated substation.

- *VUF Mean Percent*: Mean voltage unbalance factor at the bus (%).
- *VUF 95th percent*: 95th percentile of bus voltage unbalance factor (%).
- *VUF Over 2 Percent*: Number of timestamps where VUF exceeds 2%.
- *VUF Over 1 percent*: Number of timestamps where VUF exceeds 1%.
- *Mean CUR BUS*:
- *Bus CUR AUC*: Area under the bus CUR exceedance curve; higher means more severe/frequent current unbalance.
- *Voltage Under 0.95 p.u.*: Number of timesteps with voltage below 0.95 p.u.
- *Voltage Under 1.05 p.u.*: Number of timesteps with voltage above 1.05 p.u.

• **Line metrics:**

- *Line ID*: Unique identifier of each line. This is the superkey for a specific line within the investigated substation.
- *Line Loading Mean Percent*: Mean line loading (% of line capacity).
- *Line Loading 95th percentile*: 95th percentile of line loading (%).
- *Line Loading over 100*: Number of timesteps where line loading exceeds 100%.
- *Unbalance Line Capacity Loss*: Mean additional loading due to unbalance compared to the balanced case.
- *Standardized line capacity loss due to unbalance (percentage points)*: Normalized line capacity loss due to unbalance (relative to balanced capacity).
- *Line Power Loss*: Mean active power loss on the line (kW).
- *Unbalanced Power Loss*: Additional mean power loss due to unbalance (kW).
- *Std Unbalanced Power Loss*: Normalized unbalance-induced power loss (relative to balanced case).
- *Line CUR AUC*: Area under the line CUR exceedance curve.

• **Plots:**

- *VUF distribution across a grid*: A heatmap of the grid topology can be generated using one of the computed metric results for all buses and lines in the investigated substation. Each node represents a bus, and each edge between nodes represents a power line.
- *CUR heat map*: A classic heat map represent the CUR severity and occurrence for a specific substation, bus or line.
- *CUR curve*: Percentage of CUR against percentage time stamps at that CUR for all buses from an investigated substation.

–

Visualizations:

Figure 4: Example of unspecified substation issue severity using VUF violations as the metric indicator. A darker red colour refer to a high VUF, which is interpreted as a high voltage unbalance for the specific bus. Blue refers to a low VUF, while the white and light-coloured red refer to an increasing voltage unbalance.

Figure 5: Heatmap of CUR severity and duration of severity for a unspecified substation. A dark red indicates a very frequent occurrence of a specific CUR severity, whereas a white color indicates a rare instance in relation to the total recorded time period.

Figure 6: CUR curve for the buses marked in red in Figure 4, and their related substation. This figure show the percentage timestamps a given bus, and the substation mean, is above any given CUR.

Insights This service can be used to find problematic buses or lines by using figure 4 to look at different unbalance metrics on the buses and the lines, to better decide what and where needs to be done, additional diagnostic tools can be seen in figure5 and 6

Limitations As mentioned in the Power Flow Tool section, the bus data is based on the power flow computation, and is not measured data. As an extension of this, the methodology of comparing the power losses and lost capacity is quite simple and a derivative number, which is a good indicator of imbalance problems, but not necessarily a completely precise number.

2.2.3 Phase Imbalance Analyser

Phase Imbalance Analyser collects and summarizes results from Phase Imbalance Profiler and Power Flow Tool to produce per-substation insights on grid quality.

Input data The Phase Imbalance Analyser collects CUR and VUF JSON information per substation from the Phase Imbalance Profiler.

Output This data app outputs a CSV file containing overall a grid quality overview, followed by a ranked list of substations by phase-health indicators. The indicators are:

- *Line loading over capacity*: the percentage of used capacity over total capacity per line (%).
- *Capacity headroom loss*: The percentage point difference between the headroom of the line loading at the 99th quantile between the standard unbalanced power flow and a balanced power flow (pp).
- *Power lost from phase imbalance*: the percentage of power loss from imbalance (%).
- *Mean CUR*: The mean current unbalance on the substation (%).
- *CUR 95th quantile*: 95th percentile can indicator if there is problematic buses in the substation with high unbalance (%).

- *VUF infractions*: Number of times VUF has been over the specified 2% threshold.
- *Mean VUF*: The mean voltage unbalance on the substation (%).

Visualization

Table 6: Grid capacity and phase imbalance metrics

	Cap. lost	Power lost	Mean CUR	CUR 95th pct.	VUF infractions	Mean VUF
Overall examined grid	8.28 pp	4.08%	44.08%	70.54%	371	0.20%
Substation 127212	10.27 pp	3.89%	49.06%	76.05%	63	0.38%
Substation 420780	4.73 pp	1.41%	45.58%	79.10%	16	0.12%
Substation 693235	7.84 pp	3.62%	43.66%	69.51%	40	0.14%
Substation 287300	6.72 pp	2.92%	36.50%	57.70%	43	0.12%
Substation 791509	8.65 pp	4.65%	37.53%	57.20%	39	0.20%
Substation 47334	10.58 pp	4.66%	53.61%	81.82%	64	0.20%
Substation 489917	6.39 pp	4.92%	49.42%	75.10%	66	0.15%
Substation 553009	7.82 pp	5.80%	37.30%	58.91%	40	0.12%

Figure 7: Mean capacity headroom freed by phase rebalancing across six substations. Each bar shows the average reduction in 99th-percentile line utilization per line segment, expressed in percentage points (pp). The gray bar shows the lineaverage across all line segments.

Insights This data app primarily aggregates outputs from the Phase Imbalance Profiler and the Power Flow Tool, combining the results into visual representations for the user interface. The output presented in Table 6 serves as an illustrative example of the information intended to be displayed in the interface.

2.3 Results on Significant Electrification Loads

2.3.1 Detection of Electric Vehicle Charging

The EV (electric vehicle) detection identifier data app analyses smart meter measurements of active power consumption across individual phases. The purpose is to identify and register instances of characteristic patterns associated with EV charging sessions, indicating the possible presence of an EV charger at this node. Additionally, the method determines the number of charging phases, which is essential for subsequent analyses of grid impact, including phase unbalance assessment and related operational decision-making.

Input Data The EV identifier analyses smart meter time-series data for active power consumption at each phase.

Output Data The EV detection module produces two complementary output formats.

- **The primary output:** Structured CSV file, where each row corresponds to a single smart meter. For each meter, the file reports whether EV charging behaviour has been detected, along with key characteristics of the identified pattern. These include the inferred charging type (single-phase, two-phase, or three-phase), the specific active phases, and a confidence assessment of the detection. The confidence evaluation combines multiple indicators, such as the number of detected charging sessions, average charging starting time patterns, and phase consistency, and is provided both as a normalized numerical score (0–100) and as a qualitative label (Low to Very High). Additionally, a flag is included to indicate potential false positives arising from similarity to heat pump operation.
- **The secondary output:** Phase-level representation, where each smart meter is broken down by individual phases. This format explicitly indicates the presence or absence of EV charging behaviour on each phase, enabling more detailed analysis of phase utilisation and supporting downstream applications such as phase unbalance assessment.

Visualization

Table 7: Example of EV detection results at the smart meter level. The table summarizes whether EV charging behaviour is detected, the inferred charging type, confidence level, and the active phases involved.

SM ID	EV Detected	Type	HP FP Potential	Conf. Score	Conf. Label	Active Phases
SM01	Yes	1ph	No	27.59	Medium	[I2]
SM02	No	None	No	–	–	None
SM03	No	None	No	–	–	None
SM04	Yes	1ph	No	68.97	High	[I3]
SM05	Yes	3ph	No	58.62	High	[I1, I2, I3]
SM06	No	None	No	–	–	None

Table 8: Example of EV detection results per smart meter phase. Each phase is evaluated independently, and a value of *True* indicates that EV charging behaviour was identified on the corresponding phase.

SM ID	SM Phase	EV Detected
SM01	I1	False
SM01	I2	True
SM01	I3	False
SM02	I1	False
SM02	I2	False
SM02	I3	False
SM03	I1	False
SM03	I2	False
SM03	I3	False
SM04	I1	False
SM04	I2	False
SM04	I3	True
SM05	I1	True
SM05	I2	True
SM05	I3	True

Figure 8: EV charging behaviour across smart meters by charging type (3-phase, 2-phase, and 1-phase), showing the relationship between number of detected sessions and average start time. Red-circled points indicate potential heat pump false positives.

Figure 9: Overview of EV detection results across all analyzed smart meters, showing the share of detected cases, distribution of charging types, and confidence levels for detected EVs.

Insights The results (see Figure 9) indicate that approximately 30% of the analysed smart meters (over 60,000 in total) exhibit EV charging behaviour, characterized by sustained active power plateaus in the range of 3–7 kW of additional power per phase and lasting at least two hours.

Among the detected cases, the single-phase charging pattern is dominant (65%), followed by three-phase (30%) and two-phase (5%). A notable challenge is the potential overlap with heat pump operation, as around 35% of smart meters with detected EV patterns are also labeled with heat pump activity on the same phases, which may lead to false positive EV detections.

To address this, a confidence scoring framework is applied, incorporating factors such as the number of detected charging sessions, the presence of night-time charging patterns, the type of phase connection (with three-phase detections generally assigned higher confidence), and the absence of heat pump signals on the same phases. Based on this evaluation, 27% of SM with detected EV charging pattern show *High* and *Very high* confidence levels, 42.5% - *Medium* confidence, and 30.6% - *Low*

confidence (Figure 9c.).

Furthermore, the analysis reveals that phase L1 is most frequently utilized for EV charger connections, highlighting a potential source of phase imbalance in the distribution network.

Limitations Several limitations should be acknowledged when interpreting the results of this study.

First, the plateau-based detection algorithm relies on fixed thresholds for active power ramp magnitude (3–7 kW), minimum session duration (2 hours), and fluctuation tolerance, which were defined based on domain knowledge and typical EV charger specifications rather than empirically derived from labelled data. As a consequence, atypical charging behaviour, such as sessions shorter than 2 hours, slower ramp-up charging profiles, may go undetected, potentially leading to an underestimation of EV penetration.

Second, the absence of ground truth data, i.e. confirmed EV ownership records matched to individual smart meters, means that the detection results could not be formally validated, and the confidence scoring framework, while systematic, remains heuristic in nature. The true false positive and false negative rates of the method are therefore unknown.

Third, while a heat pump false positive flag was introduced by cross-referencing an independent heat pump classification study (see Section 2.3.2), the possibility of other household appliances or industrial loads mimicking EV charging plateaus cannot be fully excluded.

Finally, the classification of unbalanced EV charging (1-phase and 2-phase detections) is inherently more uncertain than 3-phase detection, as single- and dual-phase load patterns are harder to distinguish from other asymmetric household consumption.

2.3.2 Detection of Electric Heating Appliances

The Heat Pump Identifier data app analyses smart meter data at both the meter and substation levels to extract features for detecting electric heating on a per-phase basis. Machine learning methods are applied for classification, and probabilistic methods are applied to improve the reliability of the training labels used in supervised learning[9].

Since heat pumps and conventional electric heating have very similar electrical consumption patterns, they cannot be reliably distinguished using smart meter data alone. Therefore, the method identifies electric heating in general rather than heat pumps specifically.

Input data The Heat Pump Identifier consist of two sub-modules. The machine learning classifier module, and the statistical and probabilistic labeling module. The two modules are injected different inputs:

- **The statistical and probabilistic labeling:** Labels rely on both smart meter time series data and existing heat pump labels. Due to the lack of accurate per-phase ground truth, heat pump classifications from the Danish Building Registry (BBR)[10] are used which are featured in the Meter And Cabinet CSV files.
- **Machine learning:** Features are primarily derived from smart meter time series data, either from individual smart meters or from groups of smart meters connected to a secondary substation, but are also depended on weather data (also used in the probabilistic code), spotprices for the time period, and reference profile data simulating a heat pump load. Training labels, or labels used for evaluation metrics, are inputted from the *probabilistic labeling code*

Output The probabilistic labelling methods and the machine learning models produce a per-phase classification for each analysed smart meter, indicating whether a phase shows strong electric heating behaviour. The results are stored as a CSV file containing boolean classification values for each phase.

- **The statistical and probabilistic labeling:** Computes electric heating confidence values for each phase of each smart meter ID. Labels per smart meter ID are stored in individual JSON files in a dictionary format.
- **Machine learning:** Computes boolean electric heating labels for each phase per smart meter ID, and stores them in a CSV using either unsupervised agglomerative hierarchical clustering (AHC), semi-supervised label propagation (LP), or supervised logistic regression (LR) machine learning models. LR and LP is able to add confidence values for the classification outputs, whereas AHC is not.
The models are also able to optionally generate plots. PCA plots can be constructed by AHC and LP, histograms by LP and LR, and dendograms by AHC. All plots are saved in PNG format.

Visualizations

Table 9: Example of label propagation classifications per smart meter phase. Label propagation results include predicted electric heating confidence scores, and, in this case, classify *True* if confidence is >50%.

SM ID	SM Phase	Predicted EH	Confidence [%]
SM01	I1	False	0.00
SM01	I2	False	0.00
SM01	I3	True	79.17
SM02	I1	False	1.09
SM02	I2	False	1.65
SM02	I3	False	0.00
SM03	I1	False	2.06
SM03	I2	False	0.00
SM03	I3	True	100.00

Table 10: Example of concatenated statistical and probabilistic code results with confidence of electric heating appliance for every phase per smart meter ID.

SM ID	Confidence I1 [%]	Confidence I2 [%]	Confidence I3 [%]
SM01	100.00	100.00	100.00
SM02	0.00	0.00	0.00
SM03	100.00	96.36	1.35
SM04	0.00	100.00	0.00
SM05	99.99	0.00	100.00
SM06	100.00	100.00	100.00
SM07	100.00	100.00	100.00
SM08	0.00	100.00	2.15

Figure 10: Example of Hierarchical clustering dendrogram from the machine learning module. Every leaf in the orange cluster represent smart meter phases with a considerable electric heating patterns, whereas the green cluster represent phases with non-detectable electric heating pattern.

Insights The Danish Building Registry heat pump labels, used in the statistic and probabilistic code, are incomplete, are not phase-specific and may contain errors. Therefore, the code rely on several assumptions, which introduces uncertainty in the generated labels. Since these per-phase labels are used as training data for the machine learning code, this uncertainty propagates into the classification results.

As a result, the machine learning model performance must be evaluated with consideration to the uncertainty in the training labels, meaning the final classifications also contain inherent uncertainty.

Both the per-phase statistic labeling and the machine learning classification are based on temperature-dependent consumption patterns. Therefore, even with uncertainty in the exact appliance type, the identified installations are highly likely to be electric heating appliances, or loads with similar temperature-dependent behavior.

Limitations Improving the ground-truth labels would significantly enhance classification performance. Due to incomplete registry labels and the need to generate per-phase labels, the results show an unrealistically high number of smart meters with at least one phase classified as electric heating. This is likely caused by the strong reliance on temperature-dependent features, which may also capture other temperature-correlated loads.

Among the three applied machine learning methods, the semi-supervised label propagation method shows the best performance, as it handles incomplete and uncertain labels better than the other methods. Negative labels are generated based on phases with consumption patterns that show inverse temperature dependency and seasonal behaviour [9].

Both per-phase labeling and feature engineering are scalable and can be executed in parallel using Dask multicore processing, enabling application to large smart meter datasets.

All models perform best with large amounts of data. It is recommended, at a minimum, to process 5000

SMs at once for proper classification. However, for hierarchical clustering and label propagation, because of the linkage matrix memory scaling of $O(N^2)$, classifying more than 10,000-15,000 households becomes infeasible on a local setup. To work around this, it is recommended to use k-means or label propagation with KNN instead, even though these may have worse performance.

2.3.3 Detection of PV systems

The PV detection data app identifies the presence of photovoltaic (PV) systems using smart meter export power data. To confirm PV behaviour, the export signal is checked for correlation with solar irradiance data from a reference weather station (DTU Lyngby, Zealand). A positive correlation between export patterns and solar irradiance is used as an indicator of PV generation. Additionally, the method determines the specific phases on which PV generation is observed, enabling further analysis of phase utilisation and potential impacts on network operation.

Input Data The PV detection module uses smart meter time-series data of *active power export at each phase* and *solar irradiance measurements* from the weather station are used as a reference signal to validate the presence of photovoltaic generation.

Output Data The PV detection module produces two complementary output formats.

- **The primary output:** A structured CSV file, where each row corresponds to a single smart meter. For each meter, the file reports whether power export is detected and whether this export is consistent with PV generation. Key characteristics include the phases on which export occurs, the number of exporting phases, and the correlation between export behaviour and solar irradiance measurements. A correlation above a predefined threshold is used to confirm the presence of PV generation.
- **The secondary output:** A phase-level representation, where each smart meter is broken down by individual phases. This format explicitly indicates the presence or absence of export on each phase, enabling more detailed analysis of phase utilisation and supporting further assessment of distributed generation impact on the network.

Table 11: Example of PV detection results at the smart meter level. The table shows whether power export is observed, the phases on which export occurs, the number of exporting phases, and whether PV generation is confirmed based on correlation with solar irradiance data.

SM ID	Export Detected	I1 Export	I2 Export	I3 Export	# Phases	PV Detected
SM01	No	No	No	No	0	No
SM02	Yes	Yes	No	No	1	Yes
SM03	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	2	Yes
SM04	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	3	Yes
SM05	Yes	Yes	No	No	1	No
SM06	No	No	No	No	0	No

Table 12: Example of PV detection results per smart meter phase. Each phase is evaluated independently, and a value of *True* indicates the presence of power export on that phase. PV detection at the smart meter level is confirmed based on correlation with solar irradiance.

SM ID	SM Phase	PV Export
SM01	I1	False
SM01	I2	False
SM01	I3	False
SM02	I1	True
SM02	I2	False
SM02	I3	False
SM03	I1	True
SM03	I2	False
SM03	I3	True
SM04	I1	True
SM04	I2	True
SM04	I3	True
SM05	I1	True
SM05	I2	False
SM05	I3	False
SM06	I1	False
SM06	I2	False
SM06	I3	False

a) PV-related activity among smart meters
(No-export cases ≈ 93%)

b) Distribution of PV systems by number of exporting phases

Figure 11: Overview of PV detection results across all analyzed smart meters, showing the share of meters with detected PV generation and the distribution of PV systems by number of exporting phases.

Visualization

Insights PV system detection was performed across the full dataset of smart meters (over 60000) by analysing power export columns and validating detected export activity against Global Horizontal Irradiance (GHI) measurements from a co-located weather station. The analysis (see Figure 11) reveals that the vast majority of smart meters (approximately 93%) show no export activity indicating either the absence of a PV system or a self-consumption-only setup where generated power never exceeds local demand.

Among the remaining 7% of meters that had active power export, 74% were confirmed as PV systems based on a positive correlation with GHI exceeding the threshold of 0.2, while the remaining 26% showed export activity that could not be attributed to solar generation, potentially reflecting battery storage systems, measurement artifacts, or other distributed energy resources. Examining the phase configuration of confirmed PV systems reveals a dominance of 3-phase installations (55%), followed by 1-phase (31.3%) and 2-phase (13.6%) systems. The relatively high share of single-phase PV installations is noteworthy from a grid perspective, as it introduces inherent phase asymmetry into the low-voltage network, which may compound phase unbalance issues at the distribution level.

Limitations The PV detection approach has several limitations that should be considered when interpreting the results.

First, the method relies on a relatively low correlation threshold (0.2) to avoid excluding partially shaded or degraded PV systems with weaker irradiance tracking. However, this also increases the risk of false positives, as other sources of power export, such as battery discharge during the daytime, may show patterns similar to those of solar generation.

At the same time, some PV systems may not export enough energy to be detected, especially if most of the generated power is consumed locally. As a result, the large share of “no export” cases likely includes both households without PV and households with PV systems that do not export significantly.

Finally, the analysis uses solar irradiance data from a single weather station, which may not fully represent local conditions such as shading, roof orientation, or microclimate differences. This can affect the accuracy of the correlation for individual smart meters.

2.3.4 Phase-asymmetric PV and storage operation (Battery interference)

Input Data The phase-asymmetric PV and storage detection module uses a previously PV-detected labeled smart meter list and smart meter time-series data for active power imports and exports at each phase.

Output Data Table 13 shows the detection output table example for the phase asymmetric operation of the PV and battery system or the absence of such.

Table 13: Example of phase-asymmetric PV generation and battery operation at smart meter level. The table shows cases where PV export occurs on one or more phases while battery charging is observed on a different phase, despite a potentially balanced net power exchange.

SM ID	PV Phases	Battery Phase	Battery Detected
SM01	I2	I3	Yes
SM02	I1	-	No
SM03	I1, I2	I3	Yes

Insights Out of 1,423 smart meters with unbalanced PV installations (991 single-phase and 432 two-phase systems), 4 cases were identified as a battery storage device to be simultaneously drawing power from the grid while PV is exporting, keeping the net power balance. Although the number of detected cases is small, these represent a real and measurable grid imbalance pattern that would be invisible without phase-level analysis.

Limitations The detection is based on a correlation threshold of 0.4, which is relatively permissive and may include false positives. Conversely, genuine cases may be missed if the battery does not charge consistently during PV export periods, lowering the correlation below the threshold.

2.3.5 Load Profile Generator

What is it, what it does: While not being included as a data app, a master thesis [11] was conducted as a part of the 3PhaseInsight project. This project developed and validated multiple models for generating synthetic load profiles, concluding that the hybrid GUIDED-Faraday model produced the best results. A ready-to-run script (which is not integrated into the rest of the 3phaseInsight workflow) is available in the prototype environment (see D2.2 [5]). Therefore, a condensed explanation is included here. For a more detailed approach, results, and visualisations, see [11].

Input Data: The model takes time-series active power data at both 15-minute and 1-hour granularities. It also accepts a set of optional conditional parameters that allow the user to steer the generation process. These include a `meter_id` to pin the generated profiles to a specific user seen during training, a `date` (in YYYY-MM-DD format) to encode temporal features such as day-of-week, month, and public holidays, and binary or multi-class appliance flags indicating the presence of an electric vehicle (`ev`), solar panels (`pv`), and the class of heat pump installed (`hp`). All parameters are optional; any omitted condition is sampled randomly from the training distribution. Not all models support all conditions, and the conditions supported by a given model can be inspected at runtime. If no conditions are provided, the generator samples freely from the full learned distribution.

Output data: The generator outputs synthetic 24-hour electricity consumption profiles in units of kWh per hour, inverse-normalised to the original scale by the loaded model. For single-phase models, each generated profile has the shape $[n, 24, 1][n, 24, 1][n, 24, 1]$, where n is the number of requested profiles. For three-phase models, the output shape is $[n, 24, 3][n, 24, 3][n, 24, 3]$, with one column per phase. When continuous multi-day generation is enabled, the output is a single end-to-end sequence of shape $[n \times 24, 1][n \times 24, 1][n \times 24, 1]$ (or $[n \times 24, 3][n \times 24, 3][n \times 24, 3]$ for three-phase models), with smooth transitions across midnight boundaries, making it suitable for weekly or longer horizon simulations.

Limitations: While the model can generate profiles that contain characteristics of household loads and the different electrical units, it was also found that the synthetic data can be distinguished from real load data. For 3-phase data, the model especially has trouble properly modelling the relations between the phases. Therefore, the synthetic data should be used primarily for grid analysis, not for examining specific meters.

3 Scaling

To evaluate how the data apps respond to input data volumes representative of typical DSO usage, a scaling experiment was conducted. The goal was to verify that the data apps can scale effectively using Dask on a High-Performance Computing (HPC) system and efficiently exploit parallelisation across the various algorithms employed in the project. The Smart Meter Phase Mapper data app was selected for this experiment, as its runtime scales quadratically with the number of input SMs.

3.1 Experimental resources

- **Dataset Description:** Smart meter data from three Danish ZIP codes were compiled, each with a varying number of total SMs.
- **Node Specifications:** All experiments were performed on the `workq` partition of the Sophia HPC cluster at the Technical University of Denmark. Each compute node used in the study is equipped with:
 - 2× AMD EPYC 7351 CPUs, 16 cores per CPU (32 physical cores per node), 2.9 GHz,

- 128 GB DDR4 RAM at 2.6 GHz (4 GB RAM per core).

The cluster’s nodes are interconnected via a high-bandwidth InfiniBand network to support efficient multi-node communication.

- **Methodology:** The study is divided into two parts.
 - The first half was conducted on a single Sophia node, varying the number of CPU cores used across the three ZIP codes in the dataset. Each ZIP code was run three times to observe scaling behaviour and to average out random variations induced by smart-meter count and system load.
 - The second half was conducted on multiple nodes, up to 16, each configured with the same hardware specifications as described above. In this phase, a combined dataset consisting of smart meters from all three ZIP codes was used for the scaling experiments.

- **Results:**

Figure 12: Results for single node scaling

Figure 13: Results for multinode scaling

3.2 Discussion

Wall times and speed-up scale favourably with the number of cores on a single node, indicating that the apps can take advantage of single-node parallelism well for the chosen workloads. For all three datasets, speed-up begins to stagnate at around 24 cores.

Beyond one node, we continue to observe strong scaling up to 12 nodes, at which point speed-up levels off. On even larger datasets, it is expected that scaling could continue well past this.

3.3 Deployment Options for Production Scaling

For users deploying these data apps at production scale, four practical architectures are available:

- **Single Machine:** A single machine setup would be best suited for proof-of-concept work, runs on smaller datasets, and testing. Very little configuration is required and can be run directly with the Dask LocalClient, making development and experimentation simple. The main advantages are the lack of networking and security complexity, but it is limited by the available CPU and memory on one machine.
- **Multi-Machine Cluster:** This option is appropriate for users interested in scaling data apps with a locally hosted solution. It can scale horizontally across existing machines and can be integrated

with Dask through SSH or Kubernetes, while still giving the DSO full control over the infrastructure and input data. However, cluster management must be handled manually, including SSH key setup and maintenance, and if no machines are already available, the organisation must first invest in the hardware.

- **HPC System:** This architecture is most relevant for national labs, universities, or government institutions with access to shared high-performance computing resources. It can be very cost-effective if access already exists, and it works well with Dask's SLURM-based cluster support. The disadvantages are queue delays, batch-oriented execution, and the difficulty of obtaining access. Data security may also need extra attention if the system is shared with other users.
- **Cloud Compute:** This is the most flexible option for production pipelines and workloads that benefit from dynamic scaling. It offers effectively unlimited horizontal scaling and a pay-per-use model, which can be attractive for variable demand. However, data security and governance must be considered carefully when designing the deployment, especially for sensitive grid or customer data. Furthermore, effective use of the system would require oversight from someone with cloud computing and parallelisation experience to optimise workloads and control resource usage and cost.

4 Conclusions

This deliverable has presented the results of the data apps developed within the 3PhaseInsight project, by leveraging per-phase smart meter measurements to develop a suite of modular data apps capable of improving topology accuracy, detecting phase imbalance, and identifying significant electrification loads such as heat pumps and EV chargers.

The results presented in Section 2 demonstrate that the developed data apps can produce meaningful outputs across all three categories. The data preparation apps, Data Extractor, Smart Meter Classifier, Smart Meter Phase Mapper, and Data Corrector, form the foundation of the pipeline, ensuring data quality and topological correctness before downstream analysis. The imbalance analytics apps, Power Flow Tool, Phase Imbalance Profiler, and Phase Imbalance Analyser, successfully compute phase imbalance metrics and quantify the impact of the imbalance across substations, providing actionable indicators of grid health. The electrification load detection apps demonstrate promising results for identifying electric heating appliances on a per-phase basis, though classification performance remains sensitive to the quality of training labels.

A recurring observation across the apps is the strong interdependency between them: the accuracy of downstream analytics is directly tied to the quality of topology information and data cleaning performed in earlier stages. Incorrect phase mappings, missing values, and incomplete topology records can propagate errors through the pipeline, underscoring the importance of the data preparation apps as a prerequisite for reliable results.

The scaling study in Section 3 confirmed that the apps can handle datasets at a scale relevant to DSO operations. Using Dask-based parallelisation, strong single-node scaling was observed up to approximately 24 cores, and multi-node scaling remained effective up to 12 nodes. These results validate the feasibility of deploying the data apps in a production context where scalable performance is required for 100k or 1 million smart meters, typically on cloud or on-premises infrastructure.

4.1 Outlook towards D4.1

The results presented here serve as the analytical foundation for the next deliverable, D4.1 [2], which will focus on the full data pipeline and a comprehensive showcase of operational data applications. Where this deliverable has documented the functional outputs and performance characteristics of each individual app, D4.1 will present how these apps are integrated into a cohesive, end-to-end pipeline — covering the underlying data structure and data model, the orchestration of data flows between apps, and the full results obtained when running the pipeline on real DSO datasets. This will include a detailed account of how the apps are architecturally composed, how data is ingested, transformed, and passed between pipeline stages, and how the final outputs are exposed through the user interface. Together, D3.1 [12] and D4.1 [2] provide both the analytical evidence and the technical implementation needed to support DSOs in operationalising the 3PhaseInsight toolbox.

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